

FINITE ELEMENT INVESTIGATION OF THE EFFECT OF PROGRESSIVE DAMAGE IN NOTCHED COMPOSITES

Hallett S.R. and Wisnom M.R.

*Department of Aerospace Engineering, University of Bristol,
University Walk, BS8 1TR, UK*

SUMMARY: This paper presents results from a new approach to modelling notched damage in composite materials using interface elements to model intra- and inter-ply damage. The technique, which has been described in detail in previous publications, is used to examine the ultimate failure modes observed in a number of different layups made up from glass/epoxy prepreg. Due to the detailed modelling of the individual damage modes their interaction is well characterised. The analytical results obtained compare well with detailed test observations, capturing delamination, intra-ply splitting and fibre failure. The trend of decreasing strength with increasing specimen size that was observed in test results is also well characterised by the analysis.

KEYWORDS: Notched strength, progressive damage, finite element analysis, interface element, size effect

INTRODUCTION

The subject of damage in notched composites is an area of extensive research. Many authors report the need for detailed stress analysis at the notch tip in order to predict the failure stress of a given layup, e.g. [1, 2]. For sharp notches finite element analysis shows a stress singularity at the notch tip. This results in arbitrary values, which are dependent on the mesh size, being predicted for the maximum stress in the load bearing plies. The stress levels at which ultimate failure occurs are modified by the presence of progressive damage, which develops in the specimen from relatively low levels of applied stress. This takes the form of splitting within the plies in the loading direction at the notch tip, matrix cracking transverse to the load and delamination between the plies.

One approach to determine notched strength has been to use the point or average stress at a characteristic distance from the notch tip to determine failure as proposed by Whitney and Nuismer³. Many variations of such failure criteria have been put forward but a general failing of such approaches is that they require experimentally determined parameters that are layup specific. Kortschot⁴ and other investigators have used finite element models with damage inserted at appropriate locations to obtain the relation between stress and damage but this is still unable to predict how the damage will initiate and grow.

A technique for predictive modelling of the damage development prior to ultimate failure has been developed using finite element analysis with interface elements to model the delamination and splitting^{5,6}. Figure 1 shows the effect that this has on the prediction of stresses in the load bearing 0° plies of a cross-ply layup subject to a tensile load. The technique has also been applied to quasi-isotropic layups. An examination of how the inclusion of sub-critical damage affects results for the prediction of ultimate failure has been carried out and is presented here.

Figure 1 (a)Experimental damage, (b)predicted damage, (c)stress distribution with damage, and (d)stresses without damage modelling, all at 200MPa applied far field stress

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Quasi-static tensile tests have been done using Hexcel E-glass/913 double edge-notched specimens. The specimen geometry and layups tested are shown in Figure 2. It is well known that the strength of composite materials varies with the size of specimen tested⁷, and for notched specimens the notch size is a crucial parameter. Scaled tests were therefore performed for each lay-up, with the notch size and all in-plane dimensions scaled up and down by a factor of 2 compared with those shown in Figure 2, such that widths of 10, 20 and 40mm were tested with a constant ratio of notch size to width. This eliminates the effect of any finite width correction on notched strength and provides a stringent test for the analysis, as conventional in-plane finite element modelling would give identical stress fields for the different sized specimens.

Figure 2 Specimen geometry for 20mm wide specimen

The damage development was monitored from the start of loading and its growth was recorded using a digital video camera. Damage initiates at the notch tips in the form of clearly visible splits within each ply extending in the fibre direction. This occurs at a relatively low stress compared to the ultimate failure load. Additional intra-ply matrix cracks develop transverse to the applied load in the central section. Adjacent to the splits are areas of delamination. The ultimate tensile strength of the specimen is limited by fibre failure except in the case of the $[45/90/-45]_s$ laminate where smaller specimens failed by delamination and fibre pull-out only.

Figure 3 shows some typical results from the 20mm wide specimens of all four lay-ups tested. The images shown are not taken at regular time intervals but have rather been chosen to best show the damage development.

Figure 3 Typical results from the different layups tested

FAILURE STRESSES

The trend for the ultimate strength of the specimens to reduce with increasing specimen size is similar for all lay-ups. In Figure 4 the far field applied stress has been plotted against specimen width using the mean value from each data set.

Figure 4 Plot of strength vs. specimen width for all layups tested

Several different failure modes were observed for the ultimate failure of the specimens. Some failed with a crack-like progression of broken fibres across the specimen width and others had more extensive delamination with $\pm 45^\circ$ plies pulling out from between adjacent plies. There was some variation in failure modes between different tests on the same lay-up in some cases, with the 10mm specimens tending to be dominated by delamination failure, the 40mm specimens dominated by fibre failure and the 20mm specimens showing a mixture of failure modes.

NUMERICAL RESULTS

Finite element analyses of the test specimens were conducted using the explicit code LS-Dyna. Each ply has been modelled with a separate layer of shell elements. To model the delamination and splitting damage an interface element was developed. Without the inclusion of this sub-critical damage the stress state at the notch tip would form a singularity and the so the values obtained would be mesh dependent, making it difficult to incorporate failure criteria. The interface element approach overcomes this limitation and allows the detailed damage development to be included in the model using only elastic material properties, non-linear shear behaviour, G_{Ic} , G_{IIc} and the matrix yield stress, all of which can be obtained experimentally. Further details of the interface element approach and formulation can be found in references 5 and 6.

The model described above was then used to examine the failure modes predicted for ultimate failure of the specimens. Fibre failure was included by means of a quadratic strain based failure criterion:-

$$\left(\frac{\varepsilon_1}{\varepsilon_{1c}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\gamma_{12}}{\gamma_{12c}}\right)^2 \geq 1 \quad (1)$$

It was also found that the modulus degradation due to transverse matrix cracking affected the stress distribution in and around the damaged zone. This damage was not included in the original analysis and was taken into account in the model by a reduction factor calculated from the observed matrix crack density in tests and an analysis developed by Kashtalyan and Soutis⁸. Each layup analysed warrants further discussion with respect to the failure mode and its comparison to test.

Failure of the cross-ply layup occurs across the width of the specimen at right angles to the loading direction and 0° fibres. Prior to ultimate failure a split in the fibre direction and a triangular delamination region are observed in the experimental results and modelled in the analysis with the interface elements. In the model a site of potential splitting was inserted in the 90° ply starting from the notch tip and this is where the ply fails. The 0° fibres fail initially at the notch tip and rapidly progresses across the width of the specimen. This transverse fibre-failure is accompanied by failure progressing in the loading direction as a result of shear stresses that develop. In the test it can be seen that the fibre failure does not follow a straight path across the specimen and is accompanied by additional splitting and delamination to that seen before the fibre failure. The model does not have the capacity to capture these further splits and this may be the cause of the differences in the failure patterns observed. Figure 5 shows the final failure modes for the test and analysis. The finite element result shows only a close up of the 0° ply with the failed elements removed (using equation 1). The experimental result shows all plies with the damage highlighted using strong backlighting.

Figure 5 Failure of the 20mm wide cross-ply specimen

The $[+45/90/-45]_s$ layup showed a similar pattern between test and analysis both in terms of the damage modes observed and the development of the failure pattern with increasing size. The 10mm and 20mm specimens both failed by delamination only, with the plies pulling out from between each other (Figure 6) while the 40mm wide specimen included fibre failure as shown in Figure 7. This change in failure mode in the analysis caused a change in the trend of the specimen size vs. failure stress graphs with a reduction in stress for the case of the fibre failure (40mm) and an approximately constant stress for the two pullout failures (10 and 20mm). This trend was also observed in the test results (Figure 4). It should be noted that the model has a plane of symmetry and so is not an exact representation of the test case. This may have some effect on the fibre failure results but was considered an adequate simplification for the damage development earlier on in the loading since this occurs at some distance from the centre-line.

Figure 6 Failure of the 20mm wide $[+45/90/-45]_s$ specimen showing pullout of the plies

Figure 7 Failure of the 40mm wide $[+45/90/-45]_s$ specimen showing fibre failure

The quasi-isotropic layup has a more complex stress state that is causing the damage in the material and this is confirmed by the more complex failure patterns observed in tests. The model needs to take account of this through mixed mode relationships both for the interface elements and the fibre failure criterion embedded within the shell elements. Initially a quadratic failure criterion has been used but further work will be required to investigate the detailed nature of these relationships in order to improve correlation between tests and analysis. The analysis of the $[+45/90/-45/0]_s$ layup shows failure modes are similar to those seen in the tests (Figure 8) with a mixture of fibre failure and pullout. A slightly surprising result was the failure of the 90° ply by fibre failure instead of splitting in the fibre direction in the finite element model (a site of potential splitting has been modelled starting from the notch tip). This has been confirmed to occur in the tests by thermal de-ply of the failed specimens which does indeed show some of the 90° plies to have failed in a very similar manner, initially splitting and then fibre failure at an angle to the fibre direction. In both the analysis and test pullout failures occur on the less constrained surface plies. The analysis additionally shows some fibre failure, which was not observed in tests.

Figure 8 20mm wide $[+45/90/-45/0]_s$ layup analysis and test failure mode comparison

Tests on the $[+45/90/-45/0_2]_s$ layup showed a different failure pattern to that observed in the other layups. Only the internal -45° plies failed at the maximum load. On continuation of loading the central 0° plies separated from the adjacent plies by splitting and delamination and continued to carry load until they failed by distributed fibre failure that was not affected by the position of the notch (Figure 9).

Figure 9 Photograph of 40mm wide $[+45/90/-45/0_2]_s$ specimen showing distributed failure

Figure 10 shows the analysis predicts an initial failure in the -45° ply. Although the fibre failures are not easily visible in the test result, thermal depley of specimens after the maximum load but before ultimate failure as shown in Figure 9 confirmed the failure of the -45° ply. Failure in the central 0° plies however follows soon after in the analysis as there is no capacity for predicting the distributed failure as was observed in the tests.

Figure 10 Failure pattern for the $[+45/90/-45/0_2]_s$ layup 20mm wide specimen

SIZE EFFECT

The analysis has been used to predict the failure stress of the different sized specimens. It has been shown that the different failure modes described above are correctly predicted by the analysis, including the change in failure from extensive delamination to fibre fracture as specimen size increases. Figure 11 shows the mean test and analysis failure loads normalised with respect to the smallest specimen. The trends are well predicted, including the lack of a size effect between the 10 and 20 mm [+45/90/-45]_s specimens. Analysis results for the absolute failure stresses for the first two lay-ups are within 10% of the mean test results for all three notch sizes. Using the same input data for the other two lay-ups gave slightly poorer absolute results, although the trends and failure modes were well predicted. This is believed to be due to the different interaction between in-plane shear and fibre direction stresses in these cases, and work is continuing to improve the correlation.

Figure 11 Normalised test and analytical ultimate failure stresses

MESH SENSITIVITY

A significant problem with the modelling of material failure is that the resulting strength predictions can be dependent on the mesh size used. This makes the development of a general model that can be applied to different size specimens with different layups extremely difficult. A study run on the [+45/90/-45/0]_s layup showed that increasing the mesh size from the “base” analysis (0.25mm square mesh) to double its size had very little effect on the ultimate failure stress (< 2%). Figure 12 shows results for the progressive damage predicted at the same load level.

Figure 12 Effect of varying the mesh size

It can be seen that there are only small variations in the predicted damage and these are generally within the resolution of the mesh size. There is an upper limit on the mesh size that can be used for

such a technique beyond which the damage will not propagate due to the high forces required for modelling the yield behaviour. The area of each interface element increases with the mesh size and at large sizes there is no longer sufficient stress concentration to produce yielding. This may slightly impede the growth of the damage in the coarse mesh.

DISCUSSION

The comprehensive programme of testing has provided valuable insight into the mechanisms by which notched fibre reinforced composites fail in tension, and the effects of progressive damage. An analysis technique has been successfully developed that predicts the detailed development of damage in notched laminates and the effect of the damage on the stress distribution and final failure. The technique has been applied to a number of different layups at different scales. The approach closely represents the physical mechanisms observed in the tests, and is able to predict the effects of layup and geometry from a single set of material properties that can be obtained from independent tests. Mesh size has been shown not to be a significant issue, in contrast to the results with some other approaches. A detailed comparison between test and finite element analysis has been made and a good level of correlation obtained.

CONCLUSION

The experimental work has produced detailed observations of the damage modes both before and at ultimate failure. This has provided key information for the correlation of the numerical analysis and understanding of the processes involved. It has been clearly shown that there is an improved accuracy in the finite element results for assessing the ultimate failure and notched strength of laminates when the progressive damage is included in the model. The main focus of this work has been the inclusion of the different damage modes that contribute to the ultimate failure in the model. The final notched strength of an individual layup is dependent on the damage mechanisms that occur and their interaction, which have been modelled in detail. There is an equally complex interaction of stresses and the individual components have now been predicted with greater accuracy due to the included damage. It is required to further understand these interactions together with their relationship to existing damage in order to develop more robust failure criteria.

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